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Differences in Cardiovascular Risk Prediction Scoring in Individuals with Autoimmune Rheumatic Diseases

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Abstract

Individuals with autoimmune rheumatic diseases (ARD) have a higher risk of cardiovascular disease than the general population. However, the classic 10-year cardiovascular risk scoring systems have not adequately incorporated this heightened risk into the prediction equations. The growing number of peer-reviewed articles in the professional literature is an indication of how individuals in the scholastic arena are expanding in the awareness of the link between ARDs and cardiovascular disease (CVD). By dissemination of best practices, other health care practitioners can learn about the specific needs of this specific subgroup of patients with ARD. The purpose of the literature review conducted here was to describe the status of the peer-reviewed literature pertaining to ARD versus CVD and raise awareness about what variables need to be included to adequately include the ARD subgroup. A literature search was conducted using the CINAHL, Medline, and PubMed databases. Inclusion criteria included publication date from January 1, 1995 through July 31, 2015, written in the English language, and a focus on cardiovascular disease as the primary discipline. Cardiovascular risk score was searched as an overarching discipline; articles focused on sub-disciplines or other health professions disciplines were excluded. The search resulted in 265 articles. Each of the authors reviewed the abstracts for all articles and read full articles when necessary. The result was 13 articles that were then considered in depth. The articles were categorized according to their primary theme: risk scoring method (N=6); link between ARD and CVD (N=3); physician knowledge about ARD and CVD link (N=2); limitations of scoring system (N=2). Year of publication and journal were also examined. The results of the literature search lead to several observations about how the peer-reviewed literature has been used to date and how it could be used to create more robust scoring methods on predicting CVD.

Keywords

Rheumatoid Arthritis, Cardiovascular Disease, Systemic Lupus Erythematosus, Autoimmune

1. Introduction

The pathophysiology and disease progression of Autoimmune Rheumatic Diseases are mimicked by many different disease processes [1-5]. Due to the challenges associated with diagnosis and treatment, these diseases are known as a great “imitator.” Early diagnosis is essential because of the connection of autoimmune rheumatic diseases with cardiovascular damage. Even though Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) and Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) have similar symptomology as osteoarthritis and even fibromyalgia making diagnosis difficult, SLE, RA, and other autoimmune

connective tissue diseases cause cardiovascular disease. Many times patients will present with both RA and osteoarthritis, making diagnosis even more complicated [6-7]. However, having a high index of suspicion is an integral part of early diagnosis, treatment, and cardiovascular prevention.

Apart from renal damage, SLE and rheumatoid arthritis have distinct effects on cardiovascular health. Chronic NSAID therapy, hemostatic changes, and endothelial dysfunction associated with rheumatologic diseases individually contribute to adverse cardiovascular outcomes [1, 3]. Racial

and socioeconomic disparities also contribute to delay of diagnosis and more severe effects on the heart. Consequently, demographic factors and health literacy are critical factors to include in any complete evaluation of autoimmune rheumatic diseases. The purpose of this article is to further investigate which variables are critical to creating a comprehensive risk score for individuals with rheumatic diseases.

2. Risk Scoring Systems

Scoring systems are used in multidisciplinary approaches for the purpose of prediction of specific outcomes. In the area of cardiology, the Framingham heart study gave researchers and clinicians the ability to predict the 10-year probability and risk of suffering a myocardial infarction (MI) or other adverse cardiovascular outcomes. This landmark study was started in the 1940's in Framingham, Massachusetts on 5,209 original patients [8-12]. Currently there are 15,000 specimens that has been collected from four generations of this study. Unfortunately, one of the major criticisms was that the Framingham heart study that the scoring system was not all inclusive and only evaluated a select group of the population. Additionally, the original Framingham Risk Score derived from the heart study did not take into account presence of RA or assess high sensitivity C-Reactive Protein (hs-CRP). Researchers have found the treatment of rheumatic diseases play a major role in affecting the Framingham Risk Score as well, making matters all the more complicated in predicting risk adequately in this patient subpopulation [10].

Out of the heart study, there were other risk scores that were developed by researchers like congestive heart failure risk, 10-year risk of coronary heart disease, hypertension risk score, and other risk scoring systems. One such risk score included predicting the 10-year risk of atrial fibrillation¹. Additionally, the thirty year risk of cardiovascular disease was predicted using variables like gender, age, Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP), use of antihypertensive treatment, smoking status, diabetes mellitus status, total cholesterol, fasting LDL and HDL cholesterol, Body Mass Index (BMI), and hsCRP. These scoring systems are helpful to clinicians because they can help them understand and explain to patients in a more concrete way what the actual risk of a certain outcome is.

Unfortunately there are major gaps in the risk scoring system. As stated earlier, even though hs-CRP is associated with poor cardiovascular outcomes, this was never considered in the original Framingham Heart Study. Consequently the Dallas Heart Study was created to fill the gaps and incorporate this variable [13]. There are 6,000 residents from Dallas County, and this was used to create the Reynold's Risk Score. Even though this variable is part of the revised scoring system, hsCRP is a variable that is associated with early cardiovascular disease among patients with rheumatologic conditions.

The efficacy of the Reynold's risk score compared to the

Framingham Risk Score was measured by numerous researchers [14]. In one study, the authors found that along with age, LDL and HDL, blood pressure, coronary artery calcium (CAC) is an important risk factor in predicting the risk of a significant cardiovascular event [15]. A total of 121 patients were in the experimental group with SLE, while 65 patients were in the control group. In order to collect affect data on CAC, the electron beam technology was utilized. They concluded that the hs-CRP needed to occupy a larger risk estimate. The authors explained all the biases and limitations in a succinct manner. While this data only applied to a small population, the conclusions could be extrapolated to the population at large.

While cross-sectional data and retrospective cohort studies are easy to perform, in the area of rheumatologic diseases prospective cohort studies are time consuming and expensive. Nevertheless, Swedish researchers were able to establish a strong association between SLE and cardiovascular related morbidity [16]. A total of 277 patients with SLE were compared to 520 sex- and age-matched control for a total of seven years. Disease progression was measured by an activity index otherwise known as SLE Disease Activity Index (SLEDAI). In the same catchment area, the researchers found through Cox proportional hazards that the risk of having a Myocardial Infarction 8 to 9 fold more than the general population.

3. Physician Knowledge

While the link between rheumatologic diseases and cardiovascular disease is well established, physician awareness of this link has not made progress. Researchers in the United Kingdom asked to 207 physicians to complete a questionnaire which assessed their knowledge of cardiovascular risk among patients with rheumatologic diseases¹⁷. The findings from Fisher's exact test demonstrated that even though 32% received specific instruction that cardiovascular disease is accelerated in those individuals with rheumatologic diseases, only a few physicians actually performed risk assessment for primary prevention. This includes the need to inform patients and ask to make changes in lifestyle so that patients can make changes before it is too late. The researchers stated the biases and limitations of the study and explained where more studies are necessary.

While most researchers focused on increased risk of cardiovascular disease from rheumatologic conditions, some researchers found that certain therapy decreased adverse cardiovascular outcomes. For instance, researchers in Italy found that biologic agents like tumor necrosis factor alpha-inhibitors decrease risk of cardiovascular disease¹⁸. This is a significant finding because in a risk scoring system this would have to be incorporated as decreasing likelihood of cardiovascular disease.

Table 1. 10-year cardiovascular risk score prediction models in individuals without known cardiovascular disease.

Name	Variables	Advantages
Framingham (Sayin et al., 2014) [19]	Gender, Age, HDL Cholesterol, Total Cholesterol, Treatment for Hypertension status, Systolic Blood Pressure, Smoking Status, Diabetes Status	Easy to calculate risk assessment tool that uses information from the classic Framingham Heart Study to predict a person's chance of having a heart attack in the next 10 years.
Reynolds (Móczár, 2013) [20]	Gender, Age, HDL Cholesterol, Total Cholesterol, Treatment for Hypertension status, Systolic Blood Pressure, Smoking Status, Family history of premature CAD, high sensitivity C-Reactive Protein (hs-CRP)	By adding hs-CRP and family history, Reynolds risk score add predictive value especially for women, young individuals, and those with metabolic syndrome
ASSIGN (Van Staa et al., 2014) [21]	Gender, Age, HDL Cholesterol, Total Cholesterol, Treatment for Hypertension status, Systolic Blood Pressure, Family history of premature CAD, Number of cigarettes smoked per day, Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD)	This risk score takes into account social status according to the area the person lives in. Also, smoking status is considered dependent on how many cigarettes the person smokes.
QRISK2 (Van Staa et al., 2014) [21]	Gender, Age, Ethnicity, Cholesterol/HDL ratio, Diabetes Status, Treatment for Hypertension status, Systolic Blood Pressure, Smoking Status, Area of residence, Chronic Kidney Disease status, Atrial fibrillation status, Rheumatoid Arthritis status, BMI (height and weight)	Despite the challenges of coordination, development, and implementation, eight sessions in 4 European universities demonstrated the efficacy of PBL and can be useful in a cross-cultural context.
ASCVD (Loprinzi & Davis, 2015) [22]	Gender, Age, Ethnicity, HDL Cholesterol, Total Cholesterol, Diabetes Status, Treatment for Hypertension status, Systolic Blood Pressure, Smoking Status	These are pooled Cohort Risk Assessment Equations which include the risk of stroke. There was some concern about accuracy.
Joint British Society (JBS-3) (Deanfield, 2014) [23]	Gender, Age, Ethnicity, HDL Cholesterol, Total Cholesterol, Diabetes Status, Treatment for Hypertension status, Systolic Blood Pressure, Smoking Status, Area of residence, Chronic Kidney Disease status, Atrial fibrillation status, Rheumatoid Arthritis status, BMI (height and weight)	The JBS calculator allows for the estimated impact of lifestyle modifications like smoking cessation and on future risk.

4. Limitations

Risk assessments that stratify patients according to the number of defined risk factors can identify high-risk persons, but they tend to falsely reassure persons deemed to be at low risk who may have multiple marginal abnormalities. Risk models identify patients who are more or less likely to develop cardiovascular disease within a defined period (eg, 10 years for CHD in the Framingham model). This approach does not consider lifetime risk, which might be substantially higher and amenable to aggressive risk factor reduction. This is especially important in the context of ARDs because of the additional risk that this patient population has for cardiovascular disease. However, the 2013 ACC/AHA guideline on the assessment of cardiovascular risk calculator does offer an estimate of lifetime risk. Some risk scores have been found to overestimate 10-year risk of CVD. The severity and frequency of the first vascular disease event has decreased over the last 40 years. The relative effects of traditional risk factors differ according to the vascular disease outcome being evaluated. Some risk models do not include patient important CVD outcomes such as stroke, heart failure (HF), or development of symptomatic peripheral artery disease.

5. Conclusion

We have successfully summarized the most important 10-year cardiovascular risk score prediction models in individuals without known cardiovascular disease. In the context of ARDs this is critical information due to the increased prevalence CVD in this patient sub-population. However, as noted, out of all of the risk scoring systems, only the Reynolds risk scoring integrates information about hs-CRP.

QRISK-2 and JBS-3 take into account RA, but does not consider other ARDs like AS or SLE [21-23]. Additionally, as indicated, some of the CVD outcomes like HF is neglected. More work must be done to address these shortcomings.

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